

Solfeggio Frequencies

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Research topic: Sound Healing utilizing Solfeggio Frequencies Finalized Thesis articulation: Sound mending is compelling in recuperating DNA physical, generational and profound injury trauma utilizing vibrations and frequencies in life to find out new outcomes and pathway out comes.

Reason statement: This exploration paper plans to instruct people how they can utilize music treatment, electromagnetic sound frequencies and Solfeggio Sound science to recuperate psyche, body and soul. We will explore Sound mending utilizing solfeggio frequencies and I it tends to be a compelling device in recuperate generational injury and DNA.

Abstract: This exploration task inspects the job of music and solfege tones as sound mending modalities on different mental, close to home and actual afflictions. The data was accumulated from sites, 1 book and 3 scholastic Journals/Research Postulation as well as 1 narrative that zeroed in on sound mending. Data on the meaning of model sounds/images/shapes on our psyche is extremely restricted despite the fact that proof of their utilization can be followed back hundreds of years into time. The discoveries That's what confirmed that Scientific investigations demonstrate "particles vibrate against one another to shape a particle and those iotas and atoms have signature vibrational waves that can be estimated in Hertz. Original sounds, for example, solfeggio frequencies are estimated in Hertz and have been found to relate with the advanced sound scale, "shape-note Singing", Gregorian serenades, instruments and physiological reaction designs. The job of sound and music as a primary concern body instruments, cognizance, correspondence, and feeling are investigated through an extensive variety of striking mathematic, logical, and proof based speculations.

The exploration recognizes the recurrence of shapes and numbers also, note that early Solfege documentation was composed as shapes, called solfege singing or shape-note singing. The various mediums used to get to solfeggio recurrence mending through sound vibrations. Sound investigations screen subliminal reactions to sound by checking impact on pulse, observing the profound and mental state on members preceding and in the wake of controlling sound treatment. That's what the outcomes established music and sound is valuable in upgrading treatments to change the mind and ease mental, close to home, and actual anguish.

Introduction:

Energy, Music and Sound are universal mediums that can connect people internationally across culture and time. In the age of technology, it is easy to acknowledge the presence of sound in all aspects of life, and its' power to evoke subconscious and unconscious emotion. Sound frequencies have consistently been an integral part of many societies spiritual practices. Six electromagnetic sound frequencies also known as ancient solfege tones have been identified as key for evoking positive effects. Sound therapy methods and treatments for emotional and

Physical trauma are consistently being studied and modified to accommodate new emerging research. Through the exploration of how negative feelings, sounds and emotions correlate with ancient solfege tones we can identify them as effective tools for universal healing modalities. New mental health initiatives continue to emerge that address the many issues that plague our communities. In science,

we are continuously conducting studies to observe how anxiety and Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) are correlated with negative energy and low frequencies. Today, many resources have been made available for modern society to acknowledge how music and sound is embedded in our nature and has contributed to the progress of human evolution.

Discussion:

In an effort to bring awareness and educate communities on the benefits and significance of sound healing, I chose to focus on the study and use of Sound Healing, Music Therapy and Solfeggio frequencies to heal trauma. “Nearly everyone today has been exposed to the potential for PTSD-Music and sound are universal remedies that are intrinsically built into our cosmology.” (Fauble, 2016) Scientific studies prove that “atoms vibrate against each other to form a molecule and those atoms and molecules have signature vibrational waves that can be measured in Hertz. The main findings of Fauble’s study suggests that, “music and sound healing can help us release emotional traumas and end the downward spiral of PTSD. The study analyzes the frequency of Shapes and numbers and note that early Solfege notation was written as shapes, called solfege singing or “shape-note singing”. Fauble’s study determines that “music and sound healing can help us release emotional traumas and end the downward spiral of PTSD. Nearly everyone today has been exposed to the potential for PTSD-Music and sound are universal remedies that are intrinsically built into our cosmology.”

Sound healing therapy is further supported by studies in quantum physics, sonocytology and physics due to the basic principle that “everything exists due to vibration.” (Fauble, 2016) The Scientists employ the use “vibrational spectroscopy to study the energy of the vibration of molecular bonds in order to identify frequency.” (Fauble, 2016) This study will support my thesis claim by assessing the different mediums used to access solfeggio frequency healing through sound vibrations.

Through further research, I explored the use of various frequencies, as well as how our spiritual and energetic bodies are affected by sound and its significance in healing negative trauma consistently across culture and time. The findings of this research suggests that “these chants had special tones that were believed to impart

spiritual blessings during religious ceremonies. Solfeggio frequencies represent the common fundamental sound that is both used in Western Christianity and eastern

Indian religions.”(Ivonin & Chang, 2013) The basis of this research aims to identify the

underlying presence of solfeggio frequencies and its effect on our subconscious

emotions. Early Christian, East Indian, Western European all employ the use of ancient

archetypal sounds, otherwise known as Solfeggio frequencies. “The Solfeggio sounds

were rediscovered by Dr. Joseph Puleo in the 1970’s by finding the frequencies with the

use of the Pythagorean method of numeral reduction to unravel six mathematically

encoded patterns he found in the Bible. Also, East Indian classical music uses 12

semi-tones like most Western classical music, but they use Just-Intonation tuning.

Native American chanting is many times based on Just –Intonation. Although it seems

monotone, musical researchers are finding that the monotone sound has a

multidimensional harmonics within it. If further research of music from older cultures is explored, it will probably reveal Just Intonation practices were used in creating the

Music or chanting.”(N/A, 2018) Through the study of ancient histories and culturally diverse origins the significance of the types of sound healing that have been most universally employed and most effective.

Historically, Solfeggio frequencies have been identified by a set of six tones that were used long ago in Gregorian chants and Indian Sanskrit chants. It is also known as the “Schumann Resonance Frequency- This is the measurable frequency around the Earth and is equal to 7.83Hz. Ancient Indian Yogis referred to this as OM.

The theory is that when our body is unbalanced and off center it is inherently searching for this note. Man-made EMF's can produce severe dis-ease within humans and researchers in geophysics theorize that human health is linked to the Earth's frequencies." (Ivonin & Chang, 2013). Ivonin & Chang's study further defines the relationship between the archetypal sounds, 'Om' and Solfeggio frequencies. The sacred syllables and sounds in Indian religions is compared to ancient Gregorian chants and believed to possess the healing components of solfeggio frequencies. "Om" is the reflection of the absolute reality without beginning or end and embracing all that exists. "According to the statistical analysis, "the archetypal sounds evoked even stronger heart rate deceleration than the negative sounds.... based on one of the original purposes of the archetypal sounds, which is to support people in meditation practice. Indeed, to achieve a proper mental state during meditation, people have to move away from their conscious experiences and free their mind from thoughts. Therefore, people use the archetypal sounds (for instance, the famous "Om" sound) to keep the conscious concentrated on these sounds while they meditate. Then, one can infer that the archetypal sounds efficiently capture the attention of individuals. (Ivonin & Chang, 2013) These findings conclude that archetypal sounds in particular are effective in inducing states of meditation and their powerful effect on our subconscious mind and spirit. Solfeggio frequencies in particular can be used to aid the evolution of our mind's, bodies and spirits. "Change the frequency of our music and change the frequency of our minds. By tuning to 432 Hz or 443/444 Hz, rather than the 440 Hz common since the last half of the 20th century, we could retune the frequency of our minds, emotions and bodies to one resonant with the earth, our own magnetic fields and that of the universe itself. In addition to changing popular tuning back to its original frequency, we can add in tones and undertones that specifically correlate to the type of music we are creating and the intention of that music. Music to empower and instill a sense of universal love and acceptance: the tonic could be 528 Hz. Music to provide a sense of security and plenty:

rooted in 396 Hz. Romantic music for sensual evenings and truly intimate connection on a soul level: 639 Hz. Whatever intention the song has, there is a PRF that complements and expands it. Not only will music be more resonant with the natural world and human instinct, it may likely garner musicians a larger and more loyal fan base as well as more income.” (Fauble, 2016)

Music therapy and its relation to Solfeggio frequencies can even be traced to David Hulse’s research, which identifies a series of six electromagnetic sound frequencies exist and their correlation to the six missing tones of the ancient Solfeggio scale: 396 Hz, 417 Hz, 528 Hz, 639 Hz, 741 Hz, 852 Hz. “The Solfeggio frequencies have been popularized and marketed for their healing qualities, mostly by new-age healers and promoters of alternative medicines. There are however, a few musicians, as well as academics with a background in music, who discuss these frequencies. One of them is John Beaulieu, a composer, pianist, and naturopathic doctor, who offers an interpretation of the text from which the traditional Solfeggio syllables (Ut, Re Mi, Fa, So, La) were derived—that of the Hymn to St. John the Baptist”. (Schnitman, 2013) All six Solfeggio frequencies are said to have specific healing effects as they interact with the vibrational energies of the human body. (Clement, 2019) The science of sound is beneficial as a tool for people to raise their vibrations and cultivate high energetic frequencies for physical/emotional/spiritual healing and manifesting abundance. In my research, I discovered how sound can be used in conjunction with numbers, shapes, chakra healing, musical notes from instruments and visualizations to combat PTSD, anxiety, panic and manage stress/mood.

In Akimoto & Yamaguchi’s study investigates how the “differences in the Frequency of music affect the human body.”(Akimoto & Kobayashi, 2018). The results suggest that music including high-frequency sound stimulates dopamine synthesis and suppresses sympathetic nervous system activity. Furthermore, others report that listening to high-frequency music increases the activity of the parasympathetic nervous system and reduces stress. Therefore, in the present study, we examined the stress

reduction effect of music with a frequency of 528 Hz by measuring its influence on the endocrine system and autonomic nervous system. The findings determine that “frequency (528 Hz) has lately attracted attention as “healing” music. Usually, the reference tone of tuning is 440 Hz, and this is the international standard frequency (we refer to this as 440 Hz music).” It is important to acknowledge “setting the reference tone to 444 Hz means that 528 Hz is included in the musical scale.”(Akimoto & Kobayashi, 2018) When the reference tone is tuned and composed to 444 Hz to include 528 Hz solfeggio frequency music is created. The study examined the effects of solfeggio sound on levels of cortisol and oxytocin to measure healing and stress relief. This study is supportive in my claim that music and sound can be used to heal PTSD by its observation of solfeggio frequencies on the nervous system.

Overall this study concluded “that participants experienced objective and subjective stress reduction after listening to 528 Hz music, while this effect could not be confirmed for 440 Hz music. In this study, participants listened to music only for five minutes in each condition. In most previous studies, participants have listened to music for 10 minutes or longer. Therefore, it might be the case that listening to 440 Hz music for longer would evoke the stress-reducing effect, especially as indexed by chromogranin A and the POMS 2, as in previous studies. However, the point remains that even if the exposure to music lasts only five minutes, listening to 528 Hz music reduces stress to the endocrine system and the autonomic nervous system. Although the sample size of this study was limited, these are interesting data and could provide support for a new approach in music therapy.”(Akimoto & Kobayashi, 2018) The findings of this research explores how they can use music therapy, electromagnetic sound frequencies and solfeggio sound science to heal mind, body and spirit. Further supporting that sound healing using solfeggio frequencies as an effective tool in heal negative physical, emotional and spiritual trauma.

Based on the studies aforementioned, Sound healing can successfully be used as therapy for PTSD, anxiety and physical illness. Tuning into specific significant frequencies can assist with combating man-made Electromagnetic Frequencies that cause disease, disharmony and amplifying negativity. Historically, across cultures and early religions including Christian, East Indian, Western European evidence of ancient archetypal sounds, otherwise known as Solfeggio frequencies are prevalent.”(Ivonin & Chang, 2013) The research relies on the correlation between 6 solfeggio electromagnetic frequencies and with the modern music scale, ancient archetypal sounds as alternatives to medicine.

Through the study of solfeggio frequencies and its effect on the mind, body and spirit, we can come to the conclusion that sound therapy is effective in healing various ailments. “In closing, music and sound are powerful allies on our journey toward higher consciousness and human evolution. As we enter the next phase of human growth and awareness, let us use the tools given to us from our very origins and expand upon the energy inherent in them to propel us on our journey into a future of true health and well-being, understanding, acceptance and mutual love and support.”(Fauble, 2016).

Results:

The American Music Therapy Association (AMTA) defines music therapy as “an established health profession in which music is used within a therapeutic relationship to address physical, emotional, cognitive, and social needs of individuals” (Barnett & Shale, 2012). Music therapy involves singing, writing music, making music, listening to music, and lyric analysis, among many other techniques (Barnett & Shale, 2012).

Psychologists will want to make their clients aware that the quality of their music is not what impacts the therapeutic process. Rather, the focus should be on helping clients to explore their thoughts and feelings through the use of a music intervention. Music therapy is a multidimensional approach in that it focuses on a variety of

“facets—physical, emotional, mental, social, aesthetic, and spiritual” as a means to improve health (Barnett & Shale, 2012). Some evidence is provided that supports music therapy’s use to reduce anxiety, depression, and pain although the literature is limited (Barnett & Shale, 2012). Music therapy may ethically and appropriately be integrated into ongoing psychological treatment by appropriately trained psychologists.

Understanding the relationship between music, sound and vibration has brought us closer to determining how sound therapy effects the body. The main findings of Fauble’s study suggests that “music and sound healing can help us release emotional traumas and end the downward spiral of PTSD. Nearly everyone today has been exposed to the potential for PTSD-Music and sound are universal remedies that are intrinsically built into our cosmology”(Fauble, 2016). Through the use of quantum physics, sonocytology and physics “everything exists due to vibration.” Scientific studies prove that “atoms vibrate against each other to form a molecule and those atoms and molecules have signature vibrational waves that can be measured in Hertz. The Scientists employ the use “vibrational spectroscopy to study the energy of the vibration of molecular bonds in order to identify frequency”(Fauble, 2016). The study analyzes the frequency of Shapes and numbers and note that early Solfege notation was written as shapes, called solfege singing or “shape-note singing”. This study will support my thesis claim by assessing the different mediums used to access solfeggio frequency healing through sound vibrations.

Various instruments are utilized to create unique sound vibrations as powerful aids for healing modalities. The main findings of Carey’s Journal highlights the use of tuning forks on the spine to induce “relaxation, release pain, trauma and emotional toxicity”. Carey’s study states, “Each vertebra is associated with an organ or other energetic nexus within the body, so these points can be used to balance, tonify and renew the entire system”(Carey, 2003). The study applies the “Ohm” tuning forks to different corresponding chakra points and “bilaterally along the spine from the neck to

the tailbone creates relaxation, general balance, grounding, and tonification of organs and systems, continue into the sacral hiatus and coccyx to liberate unresolved issues from the past” (Carey, 2003). The tuning forks are also correlated with the moon cycles, sacred tones and interval music notes. The sacred tones are translated to music notes to create “the Solfeggio scale as seven ascending notes assigned to the syllables Do-Re-Mi-Fa-So-La-Ti. The original scale was six ascending notes assigned to Ut-Re-Mi-Fa-Sol-La.” (Carey, 2003). This journal review is significant in explaining the correlation between the 5th music interval which allows for emotional release and an ancient solfeggio tone.

Schnitman & Maria T, studies the significance of sound using solfeggio frequencies and binaural beating with numerology and symbolism. Their research aims to discuss “the overarching premise of my composition is tied to the notion of using music as a healing device, spiritual and otherwise. There were many influences on this piece. Some of the most prominent include systems of musical temperament, the Solfeggio frequencies, and St. Hildegard von Bingen, one of my favorite Medieval composers and historical figures. The following analysis of Sonic Peace highlights the most relevant influences and show how they merged with each other and with my personal aesthetics to create Sonic Peace” (Schnitman & Maria, 2013). This thesis compares the six frequencies popularized by Horowitz and associate them with a different healing quality. The numerical symmetry paired with the symbolism is used to release and heal negative energetic emotional trauma. This study supports my claims of how sound can be used to reharmonize mind, body and spirit by channeling the healing properties of particular solfeggio frequencies.

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without beginning or end and embracing all that exists. Next, Solfeggio frequencies are a set of six tones that were used long ago in Gregorian chants and Indian Sanskrit chants. “The findings of this research suggests that “these chants had special tones that were believed to impart spiritual blessings during religious ceremonies. Solfeggio frequencies represent the common fundamental sound that is both used in Western Christianity and eastern Indian religions (Ivonin & Chang, 2013).” The basis of this study aims to identify the underlying presence of solfeggio frequencies and its effect on our subconscious emotions.

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Conclusion:

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